

Tradeoff Studies for the Unmanned Free Swimming Submersible (UFSS) Vehicle

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ABSTRACT

In the early stages of the design of the UFSS vehicle decisions had to be made between fundamentally different solutions to three basic problems: the energy source, the propulsion method, and the hull shape, which determined drag. Accordingly a series of tradeoff studies was undertaken which considered the various alternatives in the light of the desired performance levels of the vehicle and the constraints of both time and money placed on the entire effort. Possible energy sources included fuel cells, various battery systems, dynamic converters, and even a nuclear heat converter. Two different hull configurations were considered for which drag differed by a factor of three. Propulsion techniques included pump jets, a method based on the Coanda effect, and a conventional propeller coupled to a variety of prime movers. In the course of the work a great deal of quantitative information was obtained both on the technical characteristics of the various systems and on the likely costs of those which needed further development.

1. BACKGROUND

The UFSS vehicle was developed as an alternative to the towed platforms commonly used for oceanographic measurements. The absence of a tow cable promised to increase the speed of operation significantly, but it also meant that the platform had to carry its own energy source. Because long endurance was one of the design objectives of UFSS, such a source had to have maximum energy content and be used as efficiently as possible. It was therefore necessary to search not only for high energy-density sources, but to consider low-drag configurations for the hull and to select a high-efficiency propulsion system, all with due regard to the time and money available to the project.

2. ENERGY SOURCES

Three types of energy systems were considered: batteries, fuel cells, and dynamic converters with chemical or nuclear heat sources. To compare the capabilities of various candidate systems, certain criteria were established at the outset. First, because of ballasting problems, no off-board exhaust could be permitted; all waste products had to be retained. Second, the power consumption of the vehicle as a whole was expected to run about

1000 watts, and an endurance time of 200 hours was considered desirable. This meant that the energy content of the system had to be in the 200 kilowatt-hour range. Finally, the space available to the energy subsystem was expected to run about 60 liters (20 cu. ft) and a weight allowance of 450 kg was established. To meet these requirements, the ideal energy source would have the following characteristics:

Energy density = 440 watt-hr/kg
Specific energy = 0.7 kwatt-hr/liter
(50% packing efficiency)

It was soon apparent that subsystems which could meet these criteria were still developmental, at best, and both time and cost constraints argued against their adoption, but these figures remained as a design goal.

Batteries. Both primary and secondary systems were investigated. It would appear that for vehicle use a secondary, or rechargeable, type would be preferred, but the lithium-based batteries, which were all primaries and hence would have to be discarded after discharge, were found to have such high energy densities that these disadvantages could be overlooked. Table 1 lists the characteristics of three types of lithium cells: note that the Li-SOCl₂ cell meets the benchmark specifications given above. The field of lithium electrochemistry is changing rapidly, so these figures should be considered provisional. In all cases the cells which were available at the time (1976) were not suitable for vehicle use, being C or D sizes, and scale-up would have been an expensive gamble.

The more familiar secondary cells, which can usually be recharged many times, are listed in Table 2. They range from ordinary lead-acid truck batteries to the silver oxide-zinc (AgO-Zn) system, but only the AgO-Zn batteries have the high energy densities needed for our purposes. All battery systems had to be aerobic, that is, they had to function in any position. This could usually be dealt with in their mechanical design, but the AgO-Zn batteries in particular presented difficulties.

Fuel Cells. Fuel cells were attractive for two reasons. They had recently undergone intensive development for the space program, and their energy density (Wh/kg) was very high. Their major disadvantages were that usually they needed a separate control system, which raised questions of reliability, and there were usually waste products

which had to be stored. Their specific energies (kWh/liter) were also somewhat low.

Two of the systems were relatively conventional, one being based on the hydrogen-oxygen reaction and the other on hydrazine-hydrogen peroxide. In both cases hydrogen gas was present either as fuel or as a byproduct, which made operation somewhat hazardous. The third was a lithium-seawater system, developed specifically for ocean use, and the fourth was based on a Zn-Br reaction which was technically attractive but was relatively undeveloped. Table 3 lists the characteristics of these systems, either demonstrated or projected.

Development of these systems for use in the UFSS vehicle involved costs in the range of \$250K to \$750K, which was more than the project could sustain. Further, except for the Zn-Br, the systems were not closed; waste storage had to be provided. In fact, for the Li system seawater had to be pumped aboard and then discharged, which would have greatly complicated pressure vessel design.

Dynamic Converters. Three different kinds of rotary converters were considered, the Brayton turbine, the Stirling engine, and the Rankine engine, wedded to a chemical or nuclear isotope heat source at one end and a 1 kW generator at the other. A thermoelectric conversion method was originally considered in connection with the isotope source, but efficiencies were so low (10% maximum) that this approach was given up. Engine efficiencies were in the 25%-30% range and volumes were not excessive, but heat source problems were serious. The chemical source was based on the Li-SF₆ reaction, which was attractive for several reasons and was undergoing development for other purposes at the time. Unfortunately the operating temperatures are very high, 800°C - 1000°C, and materials failure in the reaction chamber presented such serious problems that the sponsor finally suspended work on the project. The nuclear isotope source of choice was Pu²³⁸, an alpha emitter which required very little shielding. It had already been incorporated in a heat source designed for space probe power supplies by ERDA (now DOE) for NASA. Work was begun by ERDA on a Stirling engine-Pu isotope system for UFSS, but problems associated with the use of Pu²³⁸ itself, especially the possibility of complete loss in a seagoing vehicle, caused this alternative ultimately to be dropped as well.

Conclusion. For reasons of cost or complexity or both, the fuel cell systems and the dynamic converters were found to be unsuitable for UFSS use. Various battery systems were attractive, for different reasons: lead-acid was cheap and dependable, though not very efficient, silver-zinc was much more efficient but quite expensive, and the Li-SOCl₂ system, which would meet the target requirements, was still in development. When the Stirling-plutonium system was dropped, it was decided to power the vehicle with lead-acid batteries for checkout purposes, and then wait for

the Li-SOCl₂ system to become available. In the meantime, if a long-endurance application suddenly developed, a silver-zinc system could be installed fairly quickly.

It then became necessary to design the hull and the propulsion system in such a way as to use this on-board energy as sparingly as possible.

3. HULL AND PROPULSION DESIGN

For some time it has been known that by shaping a submersible hull properly the point of laminar separation of the hydrodynamic boundary layer could, for a certain range of Reynolds Numbers, Re, be caused to occur at a point well aft of the midpoint of the hull, and turbulent drag would therefore act on only a fraction of the hull surface. Under these circumstances drag could be reduced to about a third of the value for a conventional cylindrical shape. Other separation control techniques could be used, such as hull heating, suction, or chemical wetting, but these introduced unnecessary complications for UFSS and were not very seriously considered. The major drawback to a low drag configuration was that the hull surface had to be kept free from scratches or other disturbances and handling techniques had to be very gentle, but the potential energy savings made the effort worthwhile.

Fineness Ratio. Much of the earlier work on low-drag bodies was based on a fineness ratio (length/diameter) of about 10, the proportions of a torpedo. For our application a shorter, fatter body was more desirable, and a ratio of 4 to 5 was decided upon. A computer algorithm originated by Parsons and Goodson (Reference 1) at Purdue University and developed further by Hansen and Skop at NRL was used to generate a variety of shapes. The associated volumetric drag coefficients were then calculated as a function of Reynolds Number, Re. Figure 1 shows the results of one such calculation for a ratio 5.0. At Re = 2.5 x 10⁶ the drag was calculated to be 0.007.

Figure 1 - Volumetric Drag Coefficient C_D vs Reynolds No. for L/D = 5.

Table 1 - Properties of Some Lithium-Based Primary Cells

<u>System</u>	<u>Cell Volts</u>	<u>W-h/kg</u>	<u>kW-h/liter</u>
Li-SO ₂	2.9	275	0.35
Li-(CF) _n	2.8	300	0.52
Li-SOCl ₂ (Organic)	3.6	440	0.73

Table 2 - Properties of Secondary Battery Systems

<u>System</u>	<u>Cell Volts</u>	<u>W-h/kg</u>	<u>kW-h/liter</u>	<u>Remarks</u>
Ni-Cd	1.2	35	0.11	Rugged; expensive
H ₂ -Ni	1.2	40	0.05	Needs gaseous H ₂ (1976); space applications
Fe-Ni	1.2	44	0.11	Edison cell; cheap
Fe-Ag	1.3	88	0.14	Prototype; good recharge; very expensive
Ni-Zn	1.6	59	0.12	High current rate with good shelf life
AgO-Zn	1.8	176	0.42	Recharge with care; very expensive
Pb-acid	2.0	44	0.07	Rugged; cheap; abuse-tolerant

Table 3 - Characteristics of Candidate Fuel-Cell Systems

<u>Reaction System</u>	<u>W-h/kg</u>	<u>kW-h/liter</u>	<u>Remarks</u>
H ₂ -O ₂	720	0.25	Potentially explosive; gas must be generated before use
Hydrazine-H ₂ O ₂	220	0.25	Potentially explosive; H ₂ waste must be collected
Li-Seawater	460	0.22	H ₂ waste absorbed by H ₂ O ₂ ; water intake and exhaust
Zn-Br	260	0.87	Laboratory system; undeveloped

It must be added that this was for the hull only, for the complete vehicle the presence of fins with control surfaces acted to increase this figure significantly.

Optimum Volume and Speed. To determine the optimum volume and speed for such a vehicle, one takes the definition of Re ,

$$Re = \frac{\rho u V^{1/3}}{\mu}$$

where ρ is density, μ is kinematic viscosity, u is speed, and V is vehicle volume, and derives a value for $uV^{1/3}$ by assigning values as follows

$$Re = 2.5 \times 10^6$$

$\mu = 1.38 \times 10^{-3}$ (SI units) at $8^\circ C$ ($40^\circ F$),
and $\rho = 1.03 \times 10^3$ for seawater,

to yield $uV^{1/3} = 3.34$.

To determine u and V separately one takes the total energy expended by the vehicle to be the sum of the propulsion and hotel (instrumentation) energies, or

$$E_T = \frac{1}{2K} C_D \rho V^{2/3} u^2 d + P_H \frac{d}{u}$$

where K = propulsion efficiency
 C_D = drag coefficient
 ρ = water density
 V = vehicle volume
 u = vehicle speed
 d = distance travelled
 P_H = hotel power.

The optimum speed, u^* , is that for which E_T is a minimum. Differentiating with respect to u , and setting the result to zero, the optimum velocity, u^* , is found to be

$$u^* = \left(\frac{K P_H}{C_D \rho V^{2/3}} \right)^{1/3}$$

Substitution of working values of the constants, such as $K = 0.5$, $P_H = 350$ watts, and $C_D = 0.007$ (hull), yields

$$u^* = 2.90 V^{-2/3}$$

or $u^* V^{1/3} = 2.90 V^{1/3}$

Combining this with the expression for $uV^{1/3}$ obtained from the Reynolds No. equation, one finds

$$V = 3.5 \text{ m}^3 \text{ or } 125 \text{ ft}^3$$

and $u^* = 2.2$ m/sec. or 4.3 kts.

These results, based on somewhat arbitrary working numbers, yield an optimum size and speed for a given Reynolds No. The actual design speed was later set at 5 knots, or 2.5 m/sec. which had the effect of forcing the "optimum" Re down to 2.3×10^6 . No serious consequences were anticipated, however, because the drag coefficient, C_D , is only weakly dependent on Re in this range (Figure 1).

Propulsion System. This was considered to consist of three components, the propulsor itself, its driver, and the speed controller. Alternatives existed in all three areas and a survey was made to determine the best combination for use in UFSS.

Three propulsors were considered, the conventional screw propeller and two versions of propulsion by jet. In the jet cases the water was to be pumped either through an orifice in the tail or through an annular slot at the nose, the latter being an application of the Coanda effect.

The screw propeller was found to be the most efficient device for transferring energy from the driver to the water; at low speeds efficiencies of 70% were readily attainable and propellers of the size needed for UFSS were essentially shelf items. If high speeds or a special requirement such as noise suppression were necessary the situation would be different, and design and fabrication costs could be high. The tail jet was essentially a pump, with the propeller enclosed in the body of the vehicle and the water supplied through openings in the hull. Steering would be accomplished by moving the entire pump assembly rather than control surfaces on a set of fins. In the Coanda approach forward thrust is produced by the change of momentum which takes place when the flow direction of a stream of water pumped in through the tail is reversed and the water is expelled through an annular slot in the nose to flow back along the contours of the hull. Model experiments conducted in Britain (Reference 2) showed that this was a possible approach, but efficiencies appeared to be low (10%) and steering presented unusual problems.

The decision was made to use a simple propeller primarily because the efficiency of an enclosed pump jet ran significantly lower (50%-60%) and steering by moving the jet was more complex than the use of control surfaces.

The driver for the propulsor was selected to be an electric motor, although the same prime movers that had been considered for energy conversion were investigated here as well. The main obstacle as before was the cost of adapting them to UFSS use. Once the electrical route was chosen, however, the question of whether the system should use alternating (ac) or direct current (dc) arose at once. Because the basic power of the vehicle was dc, a dc motor seemed the obvious choice. However, the use of such motors underwater is hampered by the fact that they must either have shaft seals which can withstand high pressures and therefore absorb considerable power, or, if pressure-compensated, must be dismantled periodically to renew the compensating oil, which contaminates rapidly as the brushes wear. Further, a reliability study conducted by a contractor (Reference 3) found that the shaft seals would be by far the least reliable components on the whole vehicle. The design was then changed and an ac motor was specified. This eliminated the seal and brush problems but made it necessary to obtain a controller to convert dc to ac. The final unit

varied both voltage and frequency to control speed in accordance with the level of a 0-5 v dc input. Its efficiency varied with speed, reaching the highest value at full output.

Propeller dimensions were based on handbook calculations involving the use of the Taylor diagram for a three-bladed screw. An efficiency of 70% or better was planned, at a rotational speed of 300 RPM and a speed of 5 knots. Under these circumstances the horsepower into the water was 0.28 hp and the shaft horsepower was 0.4 hp, all calculations being based on a total drag coefficient of 0.01.

The configuration of the vehicle was such that the propeller had to operate in a kind of hydrodynamic shadow, so its calculated diameter was an effective one, roughly equal to its pitch. The actual diameter was significantly larger. The final dimensions were

24 in. diameter x 21 in. pitch.

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